

Interview transcript STE *Finance and land access*

Interview date: 16.05.2023

Participants: P3, P4

I [00:00:01] One minute. Oh, sorry. I have the feeling that sometimes my laptop is a bit overwhelmed with all the different things it needs to manage, so it seems to struggle that little bit. Um, yeah, but maybe the way we can start with an introduction round and I wait until my recording works, so maybe I quickly introduce myself. So I'm I [interviewer]. I'm currently studying at the University of Osnabrück in Germany, and the program is called Environmental Systems and Resource Management. And I write my master's thesis in collaboration with the Potsdam Institute of Climate Impact Research. And that is how also how I got in touch with you and with the the Decade of Action and with your emails and stuff like this. And the topic of my thesis is about social tipping for regenerative agriculture. Um, yeah, so that's about me. So now I would like to ask you to quickly introduce yourself with your name, your professional background, and your professional or personal relation to regenerative agriculture. I don't know who wants to start.

P3 [00:01:37] P4, you want to start?

P4 [00:01:39] Yeah, or that's okay. My name is P4, and PERSONAL INFORMATION. And my main assignment is to develop this estate together with the farmers we work with into regenerative estate. To give you an idea. We lend our 50, 15, 17 hectares to a fruit grower, conventional fruit grower, and another 25 to a dairy farmer, a cattle farmer, livestock farmer, um, which is already into regenerative practices. And the whole idea is to well, redesign the whole estate together with these farmers. So, um, well, that's what I'm working on currently. And this is also we also have a, um, a venue for meetings and staying overnight, so we rent it out. And it's also the home base of three other foundations, uh, family funds, to be precisely. And it's (incomprehensive) [name of an organisation]. And they invest in agro food companies in eastern Africa, mainly Kenya and Tanzania. And the ecology [? name of an organisation]. And they finance landscape restoration projects mainly focused on wetlands and woods and South America and in Africa. So I'm also kind of like linked to these projects. And, um, well, you could call me a jack of all trades, so I won't focus. I won't go back to much of my professional history. But, um, I got into the well, it didn't it wasn't regenerative cope at that time, but organic movement, I think 20 or 25 years ago when I started my first catering company and I worked suddenly with local food products and and organic food products and developed some initiatives in that field with short supply chains, local food chains and local food markets in different parts of the Netherlands.

I [00:04:13] Oh.

P4 [00:04:14] Wow. This is the short resume.

I [00:04:19] Yeah. Thank you.

P3 [00:04:20] And where is your estate? P4?

P4 [00:04:23] It's a it's in LOCATION. And that's. Um.

P3 [00:04:34] I know where LOCATION is.

P4 [00:04:35] Yeah.

P3 [00:04:35] Um, the northeast part of the (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) [name of Dutch region].

P4 [00:04:38] Yes. So it's because it's. It's along the IJssel. So which is the most beautiful river we have in the Netherlands. Excuse me for being so explicit, but the IJssel has two shores, of course, And we're on the (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) part. Yeah. So it's, um. It's a lot work to be done here.

I [00:05:03] Yeah. Thank you very much. Um, P3, do you want to continue? I don't know how to pronounce your name. Maybe I'm.

P3 [00:05:12] Yeah. Most people say P3, that's the easiest.

I [00:05:14] P3? Okay, I go with it.

P3 [00:05:17] Yeah, I. PERSONAL INFORMATION, I worked for a bank 12 and a half years, and after that I worked for a real estate company. Or, I actually set up my own real estate company with two friends and we built homes, houses in Amsterdam. And after that, after 25 years I changed my, uh, my path and I started ORGANISATION. And ORGANISATION is, is an estate also an estate 13 hectare in Dutch, rather small, but in the middle of the heather and the forest of Hilversum. And it used to be a convention center for the remnants [?] Strand [?] people in Holland. And in 2016 they decided that they wanted to vchange it. And I won a contest to, to make a new, a new estate, a new goal for the estate. And I found around ten other people that joined me in a team. And now the estate is still a convention center, but now it's meant for personal development, leadership, development and social development. Personal development part is mainly private individuals who come for a

retreat yoga, mindfulness, detox, other retreats, also some therapeutic retreats. The leadership development part is companies that come to us for leadership development programs, mostly around a theme, female leadership or inclusive management, or about the footprint of the company and then the social development part, the latter. That's why I think I have been invited by you for this interview is that we decided to sponsor different foundations, other foundations. We're also a foundation to use all the money that we make during a year. And also we add something from our personal wealth. We sponsor other foundations. PERSONAL INFORMATION. So the first three years of their existence, they focus on regenerative farming, I think around now or very soon they will add re regrowth to their programs and then in the end reconnect. That's more or less in line with our estate and the end goal of our estate. So that's why we decided to sponsor their foundation with the biggest amount possible, 100,000 a year for the next ten years, so a million in total. That's where they mainly run their their campaigns and all their their programs from. I don't have any experience in farming or in I have no knowledge about regenerative farming. I'm more the businessman on the background. So I know finance and real estate development and I have of course some personal interests in this field, but I have no knowledge, neither from university or from practical experience.

I [00:09:57] Mm hmm. Yeah, it's super interesting. Thank you very much. And I mean, that's not not a problem at all. I think the idea of this interview is to bring people also from with different perspectives together and also, yeah, see how we can combine this knowledge.

P4 [00:10:17] And maybe P3 is a bit too modest because it's really a very nice place. You really created together with a lot of very inspiring people. A nice place to go to and to get inspired. So thank you. Thank you for that already.

P3 [00:10:38] Thank you. Have you been visiting ORGANISATION?

P4 [00:10:41] Yeah last year I went to the Earth Day, the first edition. I couldn't join this year because of other obligations, and I was also very charmed by the manifesto you made.

P3 [00:10:56] Oh, yes.

P4 [00:10:56] The decade of action, uh, the manifesto, which is very clear, very specific, and with the three dots. So yeah, I am, I am aware, I am familiar with your work and the place.

P3 [00:11:15] Yeah, we might have met because the first year I was also there.

P4 [00:11:19] Yes, I actually we met before that, but that's out of the context of it.

P3 [00:11:26] Well, yeah. You have something familiar. I was already.

P4 [00:11:31] Yeah.

P3 [00:11:31] Okay. How nice.

I [00:11:37] It's actually also nice to connect people through these interviews.

P4 [00:11:40] Reconnect, right? That is the third step.

I [00:11:47] Um okay, so now I would like to briefly more or less briefly explain the goals of the interview and also the methodology. So in the workshop last year, I'm not sure to what extent you remember, but you looked at interventions and tipping dynamics in different areas of your system. So in education, finance, law and policy and so on. And so this interview will focus on finance and land access. So I think it fits also your your knowledge. And I yeah, kind of combine to areas so I combined so land access with the finance because yeah I just could not do so many interviews and they they had overlaps. So for me this like this STE, social tipping element we call these different areas, encompasses all resources that are needed to transition to regenerative agriculture. So this includes finance, land and also tools and techniques. And this is what this interview is about from my from my point of view. And the goal is really to find out how exactly and interventions that you already collected during the workshops last year contribute to the transition to regenerative agriculture. And I know that there's quite a huge debate around the definition of regenerative agriculture. So I just decided for one definition for these interviews and I will post it in the chat, in the chat. And if you have huge objections, of course you can say them. But if the definition is okay for you, I would leave it as it is and continue. But I will quickly post in the chat. Um, yeah, Maybe you can read it.

P3 [00:14:12] I'm going to try.

I [00:14:16] I can also read it out loud if it helps.

P3 [00:14:20] I think so, yeah. Okay. I see. I constantly see the university Osnabrück welcoming page.

I [00:14:27] Yeah in the top left corner. There is a sign that says either public chat in English or öffentlicher chat in German.

P3 [00:14:38] Yes.

I [00:14:39] And if you click on this, then there is another bar which opens. And then there is.

P3 [00:14:47] Yeah. Thank you. I got it. Okay. Yeah. Clear.

I [00:15:07] Okay. Um, so, yeah, the output of this interview is, again, a mind map or a diagram similar to the workshop, so these diagrams that you've done last year. And I will use these diagrams to analyze the effects, the effects of different interventions. And I will also try to combine different areas. So for example, combine finance and land access with norms and values. So that's why I'm doing this. And so I will share my screen now to explain you the methodology um. And it might be that you have to put the picture, I would say, on full screen to be able to read the post-its. Um, yeah. Otherwise, it's super small. Um, can you. Can you read it? You don't have to read them all now. It's just like if it's possible.

P4 [00:16:21] The blue ones or also the right white ones?

I [00:16:24] Both.

P4 [00:16:24] Okay. To be honest, I cannot read all of them. Okay. So if you could.

P3 [00:16:36] No same.

P4 [00:16:36] Just one, because it's 47 right now, if you could pump it up to 60, that may be useful.

I [00:16:45] Mm hmm. Okay. Yeah. I will see. Maybe we can. Well.

P3 [00:17:07] Oh, yeah, that helps.

I [00:17:09] Is it better?

P4 [00:17:10] Oh.

I [00:17:12] I can also.

P4 [00:17:12] If you could just do one more. Then it jumps to seventy, right? Yeah. That's the problem.

I [00:17:20] Yeah. It jumps. Yeah.

P3 [00:17:24] Now, I can read it.

P4 [00:17:26] Okay.

I [00:17:27] Or we can.

P4 [00:17:28] Ok this is fine. I'll just do some extra effort.

I [00:17:31] Thank you. I'm sorry. It's a little bit. I can also zoom in and zoom out during the interview. If in case you want to read something a little bit better, then I can just zoom in on a certain point. Okay. Um, so for the interview, I divided these elements into three categories. Um, so one category are interventions. These contain a collection of elements that were named during a workshop last year. Then there are conditions which are the blue post-its. And these are elements that I extracted from the workshop results, but also from literature. And they enable social tipping to happen. So these are conditions that help the transition process to happen and to maybe make the difference between interventions and conditions a bit more explicit. So conditions are really elements that need to be fulfilled so that the transitioning process to regenerative agriculture happens or evolve. And an example here is like farmers need access to land for regenerative agriculture. So this is a necessary condition and an intervention is how can we achieve that farmers have access to land for regenerative agriculture, and this is, for example, something around shared land ownership. And the third category is consequences. But we will deal with that later. It's kind of a free space for possible elements that result from these conditions. So if farmers have access to land, what happens? Um, yeah. And for the interview, we will go through these categories step by step, but we will also look at all of them together. Um and in the workshop last year you collected a lot of ideas and elements, and in this interview I would really like to focus on connecting these elements. So identify links between the interventions, conditions and consequences, but also identify links between elements within one of these category, for example, between two elements within this intervention category. And of course, it's also always possible to add new elements. So, if you think something is missing, missing, just let me know and I will add it. And sometimes it's also necessary to add an element to build that link between two others. And for us interconnections, I would like to follow a certain guideline. So we have two kinds of arrows, like positive and negative arrows. And if we have a positive or a positive arrow, that means that the two elements change in the same direction. So in this case, for example, if the access to land for regenerative agriculture increases, we could assume that also that there are more incentives and opportunities for farmers or for farming in the future. And a negative arrow means that these two elements change in opposite directions. So if the farmers access to financial resources increases, we could assume that the financial risk decreases. But I think you don't need to worry too much about a plus or minus, because in most of the cases as a plus, it's just that sometimes we have to pay attention, but I can also take care of that. And so the

idea is really that you discuss with each other and bring some together, and I would rather map so you let me know what I should do. Yeah, that's basically basically it. Do you have any questions regarding this process or the methodology?

P3 [00:21:38] Is it an idea that you emailed this one page? I can open it on another device and then have a better view on it. Probably makes it easier to read it and to use it as an and.

I [00:21:53] We could try it. I'm not sure I could send you this link and you could try if you want. If you can open it. Should I send you per email?

P3 [00:22:04] Yes. Per mail. Yeah. I can open that and.

I [00:22:06] Mm hmm. And should I send it to you as well, P4? Does it help you or not? Well.

P4 [00:22:18] Well. Yeah. I mean, if that's not an extra. Uh, if it's not a bother.

I [00:22:26] We have to see.

P4 [00:22:26] Although I know. I wonder if you can, because this is a MIRO map, right?

I [00:22:31] Yeah. Oh.

P4 [00:22:40] So, just send it to me. I'll see if I can. If it's easier or not.

I [00:22:44] So. I mean, in general, it would be good if you stick with with one map together. So we don't, like, talk about different things. But if it helps you to read a specific element, of course you could, you could use that. Um. So I will scroll.

P4 [00:23:08] No. That's what I thought. You have to sign in on the MIRO program, I don't have my password, etc. so that would be kind of loss of time.

I [00:23:23] Yeah. So maybe we.

P3 [00:23:24] Oh yeah, same with me.

I [00:23:25] So we try maybe with that for now. And so I try to so as much as possible and I would give you now maybe Yeah. 3 minutes to read through the elements that are already there just for

you to get familiar with what is already written down. Um, and I try to zoom in a little bit more so you can read it better. Mm hmm.

P4 [00:23:54] So if I understood you correctly, um, we start by looking to the conditions, Right? So the main condition is farmers access to financial resources.

I [00:24:07] Yeah.

P4 [00:24:09] And then debate on the three examples of interventions you wrote down.

I [00:24:16] Yeah. So the idea is that we first look at the conditions and see if all the relevant conditions are there. So for me, it was quite clear that farmers need access to financial resources, to land, and to technical support. But maybe you can think of something else. So maybe there are other, yeah, conditions which are necessary. And then the next step is to. Yeah. Sorry.

P4 [00:24:42] Yes. Sorry. Yeah. I wrote down. Oh, uh, two use, um, two extra. Oh. What happened?

I [00:24:52] Yeah, I tried to give access to, but I think it's too complicated actually. I don't know. Okay. I'm sorry. I can't. I think I can't give you access more. Let's just.

P4 [00:25:07] Access to finance, access to land. It's a very important thing. Access to knowledge. Maybe that's what you described as farmer's access to technical support. But I think access to knowledge is a very important one. Access to market is the fifth, is a fourth one. And I also think, well, that's very specific maybe for the area we are working with in. Access to farmers.

I [00:25:42] Mhm. Okay. I see. But first I will add the once you mentioned. So we have a.

P3 [00:25:54] I'd say.

I [00:25:55] Acces to market you said. Well, my computer is super slow. I'm so sorry. Like yesterday, it worked much better. But I think I have to.

P4 [00:26:20] Yeah, sometimes. MIRO is really, um. Yeah. Not easy.

I [00:26:25] So access to knowledge. And last one was access to farmers, you said?

P4 [00:26:38] Yeah, but it's very specific. I mean. Well, you know, I don't know what P3's experiences, but but I think that the percentage of farmers that are into regenerative or whatever you want to call it right now in the Netherlands is not more than 5%.

I [00:27:03] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:27:04] So that's a very small you have a very, very large group of farmers that that's the other part, right? Like to 95%. And that in some cases are conscious of the fact that there needs to be something that they need to do something different. In some cases they deny, but there needs to be done something different. And in other cases, they know that there needs to be something different, but they don't know how.

I [00:27:38] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:27:38] So you have like, these three types of farmers. This is very simple. This is to simplify things because they're just like thousands types of farmers. But to simplify things, in our experience, it's it's not. If they really don't want to, if they deny, it's, you know, you cannot get access to farmers that deny that something has to be changed.

I [00:28:06] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:28:07] So don't don't put any effort in that. But the other two groups are interesting, but you need access to to them. You need to gain trust. You need to gain beyond, uh, uh, a bias.

I [00:28:26] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:28:26] So that's why I think that access to farmers, gain their trust, is a very crucial social tipping point.

I [00:28:37] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:28:38] For regenerative agriculture. And that is also because mostly right now, those who gives advices to farmers what what organisations or persons or individuals give advices. Um, you could call them the agro dealers. Right. So those who want to basically want to sell stuff instead of give advice.

I [00:29:09] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:29:09] So, um, it's, and there's this trust relation also between farmers amongst each other. So as. It is. You have to try to find an angle to gain trust on a long term, um, to to try to take them along in this on this road of transition.

I [00:29:37] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:29:39] And, um, and that's something because mostly they speak of the four access you need, right? Like the market, the knowledge, the finance in the land. But I think that the cultural component is a very relevant one.

I [00:29:55] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:29:56] And one that is not very much discussed within also within the field of what we are operating right now.

I [00:30:05] Mm hmm. Yeah. Yeah. So if I understand you correctly, the first step is that if you want to change something regarding regenerative agriculture, you need access to the farmers, wants to change something and kind of start like influencing. It's a bad word, but, um, concentrating on them, who could change something or can change something?

P4 [00:30:35] Well, I think that maybe they don't want to change whole heartedly.

I [00:30:40] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:30:41] But they're. They. They know that they have to change due to rules and regulations. Mm hmm. So the regulations are forcing them to change. It may not be their own decision, but it's decided for them. Yeah. So how do you. How do you take along people that don't want to change? Oh, hardly. But do have to change because of the set, the context, they have to operate within. So I am not talking about the 3% that are already I mean, those are the, uh. And we need them also. They're very, very important for the whole transition.

I [00:31:30] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:31:31] Those are the inspiring farmers. We can. We can meet at the Earth Day. Right. And it's very, very necessary and very helpful. But the large amount and the numbers of hectares in we're talking about is not in hands of that 3%.

I [00:31:56] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:31:57] And even if we buy a lot of land, if we try to provide more access to land, that's still. It's gonna be a small percentage.

I [00:32:09] Mm hmm. I see. Yeah. So the challenge is how to get, like, I would call them, not conventional farmers, like with us in a way. Okay. Um, yeah. So I think for, for this interview, I would really like to focus on this as, like, more the financial, more market and land access aspects, because I think the other aspects you mentioned are also covered by other areas. So I would put them a little bit aside. Of course, if they are relevant to put a connection, we can use them but.

P4 [00:32:49] Oh no, this is this is the basic.

I [00:32:52] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:32:53] This is the basic. And the the, um, the entry point for this cultural constitution, you might say, it has to be. It has. It's kind of like a cultural mindset.

I [00:33:08] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:33:10] Uh, I think access to finance or find financial incentives is key.

I [00:33:15] Okay. Mm hmm.

P4 [00:33:17] Is key because in the end, every farmer asks himself, How can I make a living?

I [00:33:24] Yeah. Um, but that's actually super interesting. I would put this because for me, it's actually already something like a consequence from if we met the condition from also financial like financial resources and access to land, the consequences would be said the culture mindset could change. Is it, does it make sense in a way?

P4 [00:33:48] Yeah, of course. Yeah.

I [00:33:51] So I will try to note it. Okay. Nice. Um, so for me, the question would be now if I mean, if we would agree on okay, if you have access to financial resources, access to market access to land, how we could achieve this, How would we provide farmers with access to these free options? So this would be now my question actually.

P3 [00:34:21] Can I can I react on what Nicole said?

I [00:34:25] Yeah, sure.

P3 [00:34:27] Because I, I completely agree. And I would even go one step further. In my dream, in my vision about a future, there will be a time that the government, together with those agricultural multinational firms, together with the banks, together with consumer organisations and even farmers organisations, it will go to the public or they will go to the farmers. They will they will tell everybody, Hey, guys, we did something wrong the last, whatever, 50 years or 100 years. I don't know how long they are using the soil as they are doing it now with all the pesticides and stuff. But they will tell the story to the public and to the farmers. We did something that we didn't have the knowledge right then, but now we're going to do a different. And you know what? Everybody agrees. So, the government will subsidize you in changing the way you you farm. And we know it takes whatever, three, four or five, six, seven years to change. The government will take care of of of of the subsidization of the sponsoring, the bank will take care of remodeling your loans.

I [00:35:55] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:35:55] Farmer organisation. The farmer, the multinationals will take care of other food and other equipment and other pesticides, etc. The consumers are willing to pay whatever higher price and the true price, but it will. Most important for me is that it's a it is a combined effort because now everybody is waiting for each other. The banks are waiting for the government, the government is not really adequate in Holland at least in this field. We had a good minister but he went away. And the big corporations are not. Oh. Sorry. Somebody wants to ask me something.

I [00:36:39] Yeah. It gives me time to write down.

P3 [00:37:18] Sorry. I said that everybody's waiting for each other.

I [00:37:24] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:37:25] I saw it at the Rabobank where my brother in law works and a guy from my university, and they gave me, let's see, secret papers, memos, describing exactly this. Who is going to take the first step? I think that if all these big organisations, government and banks, farming multinationals, if they joined forces and they say, hey, guys, we did something wrong, we're now going to do the right way. And this is the consequence, and this is what we organised for you or for farmers who didn't know because they all learned to job from their father or from those companies and they had no clue that they did something wrong. But if I now talk to regenerative farmers here in Abcoude, where I live and I talk a lot with (incomprehensive) [name of a Dutch farmer], you probably know him, P4,

because he's the owner of the Lindenhoff farm [<https://www.lindenhoff.nl/>]. They did it themselves and they used their own money and in five years time they change from traditional way of farming to.

I [00:38:30] Wowl.

P3 [00:38:31] Regenerative farming, but they paid, they paid it all by themselves. And it was that they are so rich, they're such a rich family that they could do it. But all those other poor farmers, they cannot do it. So they are all going to wait for government or banks or other corporations to tell them what to do. So, I completely agree with P4. It is a change of mindset and culture and they need access to other farmers. But in total, for me, it should be a coalition, a leading coalition where at least the banks and the government are part of.

I [00:39:04] Mm hmm. So you said.

P3 [00:39:07] Does it make sense, P4?

I [00:39:11] I just have like one you said, like loans from the banks for the farmers to transition, Right? That's what is needed from the banks. I think it was like.

P3 [00:39:22] I think loans and those loans could be backed up by the government. You know, we have a very active government. We have those what they call (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) credit. You probably know them, P4, that a bank can give you a loan and the government backs up that loan, but you get it in your own name. You are the adapter and the bank is still the financing party. But in case it goes wrong, the government backs it up. We have the same with mortgages for people who start on the housing market. If if the banks can grant those loans backed up by the government to finance the transition and hopefully even loans with them with a lower interest rate, which is possible because the government backs them up. Then I think it's going to be much more easier to do the transition.

I [00:40:13] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:40:14] Also then, of course, with the other parties involved, the the big agriculture firms, the consumer organisations, the farmers organisations, they all should buy into this new way of farming. I think. Okay. Does it make sense, P4, what I say about a coalition?

P4 [00:40:39] Yes. And I think they're actually trying to build up such a coalition right now in what they calle the, um, uh, at Landbau Accord [? - Dutch expression].

P3 [00:40:52] Okay. Yeah.

P4 [00:40:54] They're trying to build it. It's a it's kind of like, yeah, accord. Accord is probably also a German.

P3 [00:41:00] Agreement.

P4 [00:41:01] Yeah. Agreement. Oh, it's a agricultural agreement. A multi, multi party or multi-stakeholder agreement. Um, it's not very easy to come to such an agreement because there are certain bottlenecks of course and the bottlenecks are I think the bottlenecks are also, uh, mainly, um, cultural. It has to do a lot about values. So this is, uh, well, it's, it's kind of like their opposite values. So everybody's discussing about facts, but it doesn't have, you know, that it's not a discussion of facts, it's discussion or an opposition of values. So, one of the key questions is what are the joint values? Where can we come together? And also how, for example, how we do the process here is that we ask our, the farmers we work with, what does your, uh, enterprise, with your farm look like 20 years from now? How is how do you envision the condition of your crops or cattle or how do you work the soil? How do you what do you do? What can you do to make it fertile to keep up the production without exhausting your resources and everything else? All the farmers know that if they go on working as they have been doing like the last decades, that there is going to that they are going to reach a point where the the the yields or the production is dropping down because, you know, so and then the second step would be how can we help you? And one so I yeah, I do agree that um, we need a strong coalition. Um, and I think personally that um, the government is not leveraging right now. Mhm. So what we need is a long term vision that can give some kind of, um, well, not a guarantee but a reassurance to farmers that measurements and policy will not change every four years.

I [00:43:48] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:43:49] And so we really need a long term vision and also long term subsidiary systems, long term loans and and a long term coaching.

I [00:44:04] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:44:05] Uh, because, and it takes really I do think it really takes a generation. So I'm talking 20 years in order to really turn over the whole system. So why not take that time lapse as, the field with, um, or the time scope also of the measurements we take in the policy we develop? That's the first step.

P3 [00:44:35] I agree with everything, P4. I, I agree with, with I think and, and the challenge now in Holland is, is twofold. In the early eighties, we had a very strong government with minister from (incomprehensive) [name of a party in the Netherlands], from the Christian Party, and he was able to get the employers and employees at the same table in Wassenaar and the Wassenaar Accord. And he had a strong vision and it was strong people from the government. We don't have both now. We don't have a strong government and they don't have a strong vision. So they are not able to get those parties at the same table and to mediate or to coach, to lead them, to lead that coalition to work such a two decade program. I completely agree with P4 that you need strong government leaders with a good vision on regenerative farming to invite those parties to to combine them, to make that coalition and to present that long term vision. Yeah, I'm I'm going to change to another room for a second. I hope I stay on. Otherwise, I'm coming again.

I [00:45:51] Nice.

P3 [00:45:52] If the communication is broken, but I think it will remain.

I [00:45:56] Okay.

P3 [00:45:57] I will walk to another Wifi station. Sorry.

I [00:46:01] Um, so my question, like that just came in my head is at the moment you said you don't have we don't have in the Netherlands, there is no strong government. Um, are there any other options how these important resources can be provided or can be? Yeah, Yeah, can be provided for farmers to transition to regenerative agriculture because there are initiatives that are going on and there are farmers who who do it. But would you say these are mainly farmers who who already have quite a lot of money, for example, to transition or who already have the land, or are there also other options how farmers could have access to land and finances?

P4 [00:46:53] Yes, sure. There are examples of organisations that provide access to land.

I [00:46:59] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:47:01] So, for example, uh, Lenteland [<https://www.lente.land/>]. Mm hmm. They buy existing farms and transform it into kind of like community farms. Uh, there is Land van Ons [<https://landvanons.nl/>] (incomprehensive). They also buy land and, um, land it out to farmers that have, under certain conditions, restrictions or, uh, for example, that you can land it for a lower price.

Well, that's another thing you could do. Um. You could use as a government or, no, because we want to stay out of the governmental measurements. Right.

I [00:47:49] It was just a question, because I've heard now a lot that at the moment in the Netherlands, the government is not quite supportive towards regenerative agriculture. So my question was just, okay, are there any other leverages, for example, which could be used to enhance the transition?

P4 [00:48:14] But I wouldn't say that the government is not as the government doesn't have a clear vision, a long term vision.

I [00:48:22] Okay.

P4 [00:48:23] At the same time, the government is faced with a very, uh, with a very currently faced with a huge problem, which is nitrogen. Do I say it correct? No, that's carbon. Stickstoff.

I [00:48:39] Nitrogen.

P4 [00:48:43] Nitrogen, Yeah. So the nitrogen, every everything's focused on the nitrogen crisis right now.

I [00:48:49] Okay.

P4 [00:48:50] Uh, and to, that's a huge problem right now. I mean, that's politically a huge problem. I don't think it covers the whole problem. But we also have this, you know, tunnel vision that we focus on that specific. And there is a a fund, a governmental reservation for €24 billion.

I [00:49:12] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:49:12] To pay for the transition. But the problem is that nobody wants to invest anything if they don't have long term guarantees. On what? What is the long term policy? Um, so it's, um, because they the risk, the financial risks are too high. If you invest, like in a new stable, you know, with all these innovative technologies, it costs you like €4 or €5 million. A lot of farmers invested in these types of technologies, innovations. Turns out that, um, they're not adequate. They're not adequate. And so they cannot meet certain, um, requirements, legal or environmental requirements.

I [00:50:16] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:50:16] So. And the banks are not willing to pay them to, to. How do you say that? Um, um, (incomprehensive - Dutch expression), uh, to abolish the loans they lent, like, the say. (incomprehensive) the loans they lent.

I [00:50:40] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:50:40] Or give some kind of.

P3 [00:50:43] To write them off, actually.

P4 [00:50:44] Write them off. Right. So that could be if you. What could be a very interesting intervention, could be if the banks would be willing to write off an amount of the loans or the debts that farmers have or they could jointly create kind of like a fund to. A financial fund to finance and incentivize farmers. Not necessarily. Well, yeah. Uh, primarily with loans. I mean, very interesting loans. If the farmers are committed to a certain type of transition. But then you would stay away from the subsidiary subsidiary system of, um, the Dutch government or the European government.

I [00:51:48] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:51:48] And you make it more like a, uh. A um. Yeah.

I [00:51:55] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:51:57] That could be. But you would still stay within the system.

P3 [00:52:01] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:52:02] Ideally. Ideally. But that's ideally. Mm hmm. You would start kind of like a farmers bank the way the Rabobank [<https://www.rabobank.de/>] one started.

I [00:52:14] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:52:15] So that farmers themselves put their money in a bank and they would lend it out to other farmers. So that's. That's. I mean, that's like the good the that's the primary, I would think. But I'm talking here to somebody who worked for 20 years. So maybe this is a very, very stupid suggestion, but.

P3 [00:52:43] No, it's not.

P4 [00:52:46] Um, so that could be an incentive. And another one is also to try to find other sources of, um, financial, uh, uh, rewards of the services that farmers provide.

I [00:53:07] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:53:10] Yeah.

P4 [00:53:12] But farmers access to financial resources because that's your main question, right?

I [00:53:18] Yeah, I just I think what we just discussed, the financial (incomprehensive). I forgot another one. Um.

P3 [00:53:32] You know, you have. Don't you have two in the financing, let's say challenges? You have two challenges. One is financing the transition, and the second one is financing the new business. Uh, the third one of course is writing down the old finance. So it's actually three challenges. It is what to do with the current loans and how to finance the transition. And then the third one is how to grant new loans.

I [00:54:01] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:54:01] Those three guarantees you need to tackle all three at once because they're all inter-related.

I [00:54:07] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:54:08] And the farmers will never take the risk that one out of three or two out of three are not covered. You need to cover all three.

I [00:54:17] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:54:19] That's why the banks are so needed. Yeah, the government is needed because the government is the only one. I mean, we did the same with Corona. I mean, if we are able to help so many, so many other companies and survive from the corona crisis, we can also help those that is it, 70,000 farmers in the Netherlands who make the transition?

I [00:54:42] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:54:44] I'm. I'm sure we can.

P4 [00:54:47] So maybe I think it's very interesting. A very smart what you say about the three stages. Right. Yeah. So you have the stages of financing to to, uh, how do you call it? Uh, write off?

P3 [00:55:03] Yeah. First. Yeah. Yeah. So what to do with the existing loans?

I [00:55:07] Yeah. Yeah, I tried to capture this. So, write off the current loan. Okay. Go. Write off current loans. Right. That was one of the. Okay.

P3 [00:55:19] Yeah, write off or you restructure them, but you, you need to do something.

I [00:55:24] Mm hmm.

P3 [00:55:25] Because if you have 70,000 farmers, which with, let's say, 1 million average loan per farmer or so, that's like 7 billion or 70 billion. I cannot make the math. Yeah, but 70,000 times 1 million is the current situation. Then you need, per farmer at least a million or two to make the transition towards the new way of farming. I don't know. I'm just making up numbers. Maybe half of it. But. But that's the second phase. And then the third phase is. Then. Then if you are in that new phase, you need your and your working capital, your going concern financing. So all three you have tackled all at once or in one program.

I [00:56:09] Yeah I see.

P4 [00:56:11] So yeah that's, that's very, that's very helpful because I could think if you if you make it like if you take the perspective of a coalition, as you mentioned before. What stakeholders or what parties within a coalition could take responsibility for what part of this financing stage? So you could say, like the transition, I can imagine that the transition itself is mainly a governmental responsibility.

P3 [00:56:44] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:56:45] And I'm not sure about the first stage, but I think that the last stage is really something for banks and maybe also like corporations. And the first would be like, but you're the finance men. If I can imagine that that's a joint effort of banks and governments, because if the governments take the whole risk, I mean, that would be just like the same as they did in the bank crisis in, what was it, 2008?

I [00:57:18] Mm hmm.

P4 [00:57:19] But that that eventually it's a public. It's public funding.

I [00:57:26] Yeah.

P4 [00:57:27] If the banks take all the risks.

I [00:57:30] Yeah. I find it super interesting because I just thought of like we also have this, like, post-it of access to market. And for me, this also relates to this third component of how can the business be financed after the transition? I mean, they need to be like a market access for regenerative products. That's what how I see it. And for me, this kind of belongs to this third path that you mentioned, right? So I also really like this distinguishing between these three aspects.

P4 [00:58:04] Yeah, it's very helpful.

I [00:58:05] Yeah.

P3 [00:58:10] Thank you. And I'm glad I can at least add something. Because when you started, I had no clue. I thought, Oh, I'm not the right guy in the field. And I'm happy that you, that I can add something.

I [00:58:22] Seems good for me. Um, yeah. I mean, my unfortunately, my laptop is lacking today, so I was not able to capture everything you said, But I will definitely listen to the interview after, um. Yeah. Again. And try to clean it up and to capture everything you said. So it's okay. I see that. And I think for me, the question I still have is, um, why is it not happening at the moment? So what are the like? I mean, we already have one kind of problem or barrier or challenge which are the opposite values. And yeah, I think that's quite an important one. But can you also think of other. Mm. Yeah. Kind of barriers, why it's not really happening at the moment or do you think it's already happening and we just have to be patient.

P3 [00:59:25] You know, I can think of often the risks are not equally and not fairly spread out and the risks are at different parties. And those different parties, because of the risk, can have opposite opposite purposes, opposite, how do I say it, belonging [? - Dutch expression] and a lots of belongings [? - Dutch expression]. What's this in English?

P4 [00:59:50] Shares of the same, um, benefits.

P3 [00:59:55] Yeah. They have opposite benefits. Yeah. I mean the easiest one of course is the bank, because if you transition to another way of agricultural farming and, and the bank as a loan that has to be written off. But the same is with the, with the corporation that makes pesticides. But I think that because the risks are so spread out are so, you know, differently spread out and not fairly.

I [01:00:27] Mm hmm.

P3 [01:00:30] It's not happening.

I [01:00:31] Okay.

P3 [01:00:32] Or maybe it is. Maybe P4 knows more. But I have the feeling that people are still waiting, waiting on each other. There are small initiatives like what you are doing or what Lenteland is doing or other very small scale initiatives. But large corporations and the large farmers, I don't think they are really changing now, are they P4? I have no clue, actually.

P4 [01:00:57] No, because, uh, there's a lot at there's a lot at stake for them.

P3 [01:01:04] Yeah. I mean, there's a lot at stake.

P4 [01:01:06] There's a lot of at stake. So financially, economically, so the economic structures right now and, um, so the big agro corporates, uh, they, they can, they can lose a lot of their market potential if they cannot sell their pesticides or their, uh, so they have a strong lobby of them.

P3 [01:01:32] Yeah.

P4 [01:01:32] So that's a barrier, a strong lobby. And um, so that's one thing. Um. But what helps us right now is, uh, until now, I don't know if that's going to change, but you can see that the European Union is in his, in its regulations. It can help us. That's one thing. And another very interesting instrument right now is everything that they're trying to do by law. So they try to, um. Uh, how do you think they take, they, they they force governments to take responsibility for their goals and, um, force them by law to, to, um, to implement certain policy that makes it that makes it, that makes those goals reachable.

P3 [01:02:41] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:02:43] A certain type of justification of the whole process, which is very interesting right now. So, for example, the whole nitrogen crisis we have right now has been initiated by an NGO that forced the Dutch government.

I [01:03:02] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:03:03] to reach the goals in 2030. Um, so. That's a barrier, because that's a way where you can fight the system by using the tech to the possibilities within the system.

I [01:03:26] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:03:29] And another barrier. If you if you look financially, I. What might be another financial barrier right now? Yeah, well, another financial barrier is that, um, ground prices are rocketing sky high. So. Uh, but that's maybe.

P3 [01:03:54] Do the old farmers also have a problem with that, because I thought that most of the 70,000 farmers are owning the land already for generations. Is a problem for the old one or only for the new ones, for the new entrants?

P4 [01:04:15] Uh, well, specifically for the new entrants.

P3 [01:04:20] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:04:24] No. Well, what what's the problem with the old ones is that they they don't have successors. So what you see right now is what's, that's happening here also, that, um, it's not financially, not always very interesting to sell your land.

I [01:04:44] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:04:45] Um, so what they do in order to provide some income for the rest of their lives is to make solar meadows. So to lend out their land for solar.

I [01:04:58] Uh, wow. Interesting. Okay.

P4 [01:05:02] That's a very. And that's. That's a really nice income for farmers.

I [01:05:06] Mhm.

P4 [01:05:08] But on a landscape level. That's, that's, that has great impact. But I'm still, I'm still chewing on the question what are. Because that's the question, right? What are barriers for farmers for access to financial resources?

I [01:05:24] Yeah.

P4 [01:05:28] I think a huge barrier is inconsistent policy because if you do an investment and you do it, you need financial resources to do a huge investment and you don't know if the the investment you make is in line with policy. Let's say in in five or ten years, it can be annulled. That's what's happening right now with a lot of stables. Now you invest like millions. And then it turns out that it doesn't meet the requirements, the environmental requirements, the current environmental requirements. So basically, you disinvested.

I [01:06:23] Mm hmm. Yea it makes sense.

P3 [01:06:28] I think if I was a farmer now, I would never dare to take the risk. If I'm a farmer. And you know what their current income is? It's quite high. It used to be very low years and years, but currently it's quite high. I, I would also not take the risk. At least I would not be in the first ten or 20%. I would first wait until others prove.

I [01:06:50] Mm hmm. Okay.

P3 [01:06:52] Yeah. That the transition works and that the government really what P4 said has a long term vision and keeps promise and doesn't change it four years later and that the two big corporations are are in the coalition, and the two banks are also in the coalition.

I [01:07:05] Mm hmm.

P3 [01:07:06] I, I would come in the second two in the third phase, but never in the first phase.

P4 [01:07:12] And that's precisely what's happening right now. I mean, everybody's nobody's putting the cards on the table.

I [01:07:21] Mm hmm.

P3 [01:07:21] I can imagine.

P4 [01:07:23] Nobody is. Uh, applications for loans are, uh, way time low. Nobody wants to sell their land. Uh, and probably a lot of them, they just are waiting until. Okay, so what's going to happen with me? Can I stay? Do I have to go? Because that's also what they. So they they're facing with a lot of that's probably the main barrier right now. Too much insecurity.

P3 [01:07:55] Mm hmm. Yeah.

P4 [01:07:58] And so there's a lot of insecurity because nobody knows how policy's going to look like for let's say, the next couple of years. So if there is so much uncertainty, you're not going to invest.

I [01:08:11] Yeah. Okay. So you would say.

P4 [01:08:15] And loans will not be given because there is so much insecurity.

P3 [01:08:19] Yeah, I see. It's like. So what what you would say what is needed to make this whole happen is really a long term vision on how we want to transition to regenerative agriculture, to give the banks safety and to give the farmers safety. That's why I it's my kind of main takeaway from what you said.

P4 [01:08:43] Yeah, I think that is a correct uh, summary.

I [01:08:47] Yeah. Nice. And so we have, um. Yeah. 4:15 now. I don't know P4 if you have to go, what your time constraints are.

P4 [01:09:00] I'll just inform somebody that I will just stick around for another 15 minutes. Is that okay?

I [01:09:06] Nice. Yeah. I think we will be finished in 15 minutes.

P4 [01:09:11] Yeah.

I [01:09:12] Nice. Meanwhile, P3, do you have any, points to add like I mean, I think we already discussed a lot. But if you look at what we already wrote down and.

P3 [01:10:02] So there is one thing. You know, there's one box that that that triggered me. That's the true price, true pricing.

I [01:10:13] Yeah, it's.

P3 [01:10:15] There Again, we need kind of a coalition or at least joint effort of several parties.

I [01:10:23] Mm hmm.

P3 [01:10:24] I think that through pricing can only be started, can only be launched when the government and the consumer organisations join efforts. I mean, the government can, of course, by the value added tax to VAT and give a direction. And they can they can use 0% and 9% and a 21% that's already 21% difference between zero and 21 and already gives some direction towards true pricing. And then the consumer organisations um also, let's say, make the minds ready of consumers that regenerative products are well, maybe still that these more expensive or I don't know why in another price category. But are needed for the future of our planet, because currently consumers are also waiting. I mean I'm now doing this for the last five years since 2018. And I have I still have to convince my wife to buy biological articles. I mean, the traditional families have sorry for that, but I have to convince her to buy biologic because you see now sometimes it's two times or even three times as expensive. But I think that that's the true price of a strawberry or a package of milk or whatever.

I [01:12:01] Mm hmm.

P3 [01:12:02] But I'm so I'm triggered about a true pricing because I see in reality, I, I read in, in a research article that when people enter the supermarket, 75% of the people, they say to themselves, today, I'm going to buy healthy and fair products. So low fat, low sugar and also health. So also fair products and like biological and we we used to have great (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) well I'm going to buy them and then when they are in the section of the supermarket and they really have to make the choice and they see the (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) banana next to a Chiquita banana and the Chiquita is the traditional one is half the price of the (incomprehensive - Dutch expression) half out of the 75%, only 25% actually put the biological banana in its supermarket basket. So so there is a big gap between what people think is good for themselves and for the world and what they can afford or what they are willing to pay for once they are in front of the section where they see both products, the biological one or the regenerative one and the one from the traditional producer, that's half the price.

I [01:13:22] Yeah, sure.

P3 [01:13:24] So government can do something with the value added tax, but also I think consumer organisations should do something with preparing the minds that this is our new way of spending

our money. I mean, now maybe we spend 10% on food and 10% on holidays and 20% on electronics. I don't know. But it should be the other way around. It should be 20% spent on food and may be 5% on holiday and 10% on electronics. We have to reeducate not only the farmers in how to farm, but also the consumers in what the true price of food is.

I [01:14:01] Mm hmm.

P3 [01:14:02] But that's why I was triggered about that box.

I [01:14:04] No, I think it's a it's an important add-on. And I will quickly add educate consumers.

P3 [01:14:14] Do you agree, P4?

P4 [01:14:16] Yes, definitely. But I think there's one chain in the chain. One how you call it, um, part in the chain.

I [01:14:27] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:14:29] Part in the chain that is also crucial in this whole issue or subject. And these are the the off takers and the supermarkets.

I [01:14:45] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:14:48] So it's very. It's not easy for a farmers to set the price. It's the off takers that set the price.

I [01:15:01] Um.

P3 [01:15:01] Yeah. Okay.

P4 [01:15:03] So the true pricing, it already starts there.

P3 [01:15:08] Hmm.

I [01:15:10] So what? So what would be needed to like, um, you said that the off takers need to voluntarily, in a way, increase the price or decrease the price for a regenerative product and increase the price for a conventional product. That's.

P4 [01:15:31] Well, maybe. I don't know. That's something I would really have to dive into somewhat more. Mm hmm. But I think that every every farmer does his individual negotiations with these off takers.

I [01:15:43] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:15:44] But what if they would be just like a corporation? Um, they would do it on a on a larger scale. So everybody that grows potatoes, if they could join forces all together and they set, they could set, like, a minimum price so that the negotiation force could be much bigger, much bolder than it is right now.

I [01:16:15] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:16:17] But I also know, for example, the farmers we work with, a lot of them are under contracts. And the price is set by the off-takers in the supermarkets.

I [01:16:35] Okay.

P4 [01:16:35] And I can understand it because once you have a contract, you have a guaranteed income, whatever, whatever the, the the yields you have that year.

I [01:16:47] Mm hmm. I see.

P4 [01:16:54] I don't know. This the. I do know that there's something not in balance. In that whole, uh, supply, supply chain or demand and offer and the negotiation power. But I, I, I'm not, um, into it enough yet to say something smart about it.

I [01:17:18] Well, no, but it's really a good. Yeah, a good element, I would say. And, I mean, I could also research it again for my thesis, so it's good to have it in mind and to have captured it. And so I think I would like to wrap it up a bit. So maybe a few or I don't know if you need time, but do you have any last things that are not already said, not already captured, that you want to have in there or that you want to have said, um, before finishing?

P3 [01:17:56] Yeah, I have a question. That's a very philosophical one, but I'm I'm sure you cannot answer that. I ask it many times already and I have no clue if the answer is is around if it is already present. If we go from traditional farming in the current scale of farming to regen, regenerative farming, are the technical developments and is the amount of land and is the amount of people that are willing to do let's say, are all the resources present or available to make the transition and to

feed, let's say, seven or 8 billion people. Let's say, that the world population grows to seven or eight or it always was ten, but now seven or eight, I just heard in 2100. Is regenerative farming able to produce enough food for those seven or 8 billion people given the current state of the well, the countries, the soil and everything? Or do you need vertical agricultural systems with real farming flats, or do you still need pesticides because you just need more volume from that same square meter? And the Dutch are, of course, brilliant in increasing the volume to record levels, be it milk from a cow 35 liters a day, or be it tomatoes from one square centimeter. But in case all those technical developments are implemented, do we, with the current, you know, farming systems, do we have enough volume to feed all those markets, all those people? That's my philosophical question. And I hope the answer is yes. I hope its yes.

P4 [01:20:11] Of course, the answer is yes.

I [01:20:12] Yes, yes.

P4 [01:20:13] Yes, of course we can. But it requires some adjustments and requires adjustments in our diet.

I [01:20:23] Mm hmm.

P3 [01:20:24] Okay.

P4 [01:20:25] And it requires adjustment in, um, what we grow and what we eat. Um, it maybe also requires some adjustments in spatial planning.

I [01:20:45] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:20:48] And it requires also probably some adjustments and this is the elephant in the room. In birth planning.

P3 [01:21:01] Yeah.

P4 [01:21:02] But that's a no go area in whatever discussion.

P3 [01:21:06] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:21:07] Uh, so if we can stick to the the technical part, I think. Yeah. If we change, um. If we change the way we. If we grow, if we change our diet and we look, um, we grow, um, geographically

specific species. Like. There are some very nice interventions right now in Africa where they grow more, um, um, indigenous types of grains. For example, camut [? - crop species in Africa], which is which can survive far more better in typical geographical circumstances than the ones we imported. So that would be like, um. Uh, yeah. Working with other species, I think that could help. But also, uh, probably also work with some more robotised technical solutions that are at hand. Because I think that one of the major threats is the fact that nobody wants to farm anymore. Except a small group of idealists or romantics and then we go back to nature movement that you see right now. And what I hope is that this is not a hype or a fling, but this is a very conscious decision made by people to really, uh, change that. They really want to be active in this field, not only for a couple of years, but for a lifetime.

I [01:23:07] Mm hmm.

P4 [01:23:10] So and I know that, for example, LTO [<https://www.lto.nl/over-lto/english/>], P3, you know that. It's starting a campaign right now. LTO is the farmers organisation, the biggest farmers organisation organisation we have in the Netherlands is starting a is it really starting a campaign right now. Because they see that a lot of farmers, 30% of farmers age 55 or older, do not have a successor.

I [01:23:40] Mm hmm. Yeah.

P4 [01:23:42] But that's so. And that's not only in the Netherlands. That's a European problem.

I [01:23:47] Yeah. Yeah.

P4 [01:23:50] So how are we going to make farming sexy again?

I [01:23:56] Yeah.

P4 [01:23:57] And I hope. We have nice examples of course. I mean, you know them, Bodemzicht, they're doing a great job, but how can we make it accessible and desirable for a larger group of people?

I [01:24:13] Mm hmm. Yeah.

P3 [01:24:16] Yeah.

I [01:24:17] Yeah. So from my. So from what I have read so far, um, it's even necessary to transform the agricultural system. So because you ask if regenerative farming is able to produce enough food, and I think it's maybe even necessary, um, because it's all in this debate of like planetary boundaries and, yeah, concepts like this. But if we continue farming in a conventional way, we will exceed certain boundaries and not able to produce enough food anymore. So at one point we need to change the farming system to be able to continue feeding billions of people. So yeah, um, yeah, but I think it's, as you said, Nicole, it needs, of course, adjustments and also changes in your daily life and that's I think, super hard to, to have.

P4 [01:25:20] Yeah, Well, once again, it all comes down to values.

I [01:25:24] Yeah.

P4 [01:25:24] Um, but that's a tough one. Yeah, that's a tough one. The value change.

I [01:25:29] Value change. Yes. Okay. I think we are almost done. Or we are done now. Thank you very much.

P4 [01:25:36] And thank you.

I [01:25:39] I just had one little question. I will try to make, to clean everything up and to produce a great one which captures all of the things you mentioned. And I would really like to send it to you and get your feedback. Is it okay for you?

P3 [01:25:58] Yeah, for sure.

I [01:25:59] Nice. So perfect. And yeah, and we've said I so I think I'm I don't have any questions anymore so you you are freed from the interview.

P4 [01:26:10] Good luck with your thesis.

I [01:26:13] Thank you. And thank you so much for this talk. It was super interesting for me.

P4 [01:26:19] Okay. Well, I hope it was helpful and nice to reconnect with you.

P3 [01:26:27] Yes, it was. What is the name again? P4?

P4 [01:26:31] ORGANISATION

P3 [01:26:34] ORGANISATION. Okay.

P4 [01:26:34] Yeah. But we're still very much in progress, so I'm very much over the radar with what I'm doing here right now.

P3 [01:26:43] And it is in LOCATION.

P4 [01:26:45] LOCATION.

P3 [01:26:47] LOCATION. Yeah, I will stop by next time I'm around.

P4 [01:26:50] You give me a call.

P3 [01:26:53] I will.

P4 [01:26:54] Are you on LinkedIn?

P3 [01:26:56] Yes.

P4 [01:26:57] Okay, so I'll send you. Uh uh uh uh, uh. How do you say? An invitation? Yeah, I think so.

I [01:27:05] Thank you. Very fine.

P3 [01:27:08] Thank you.